

Proactive and Reactive Styles of Palestinian Presidents Leadership in Times of Crisis

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Abstract

Crises are unavoidable which makes response an imperative matter. Thus, the proactive style becomes an indispensable part of the readiness and preparedness in any potential crisis and can help prevent it. Besides, the reactive style is still important to deal effectively with a crisis especially regarding its recovery. Proactive and reactive styles were needed by Palestinian Presidents due to the occurrence of various crises faced by them. This study examines both proactive and reactive styles used by the Palestinian Presidents leadership during crisis. Besides, it examines how the Palestinian Presidents used these styles to deal with different crises at different times. This study used content analysis on the news stories from the New Straits Times. A total of 313 stories from 1996 to 2016 pertaining to proactive and reactive styles used by Palestinian Presidents were found. The stories that included reactive style figured 67.7%, while the stories that included proactive style totaled 32.3%. For President Arafat, a total of 63% of the stories included reactive style compared to 37% of the stories that included proactive style. For President Abbas, a total of 78.4% of the stories contained reactive style compared to 21.6% that contained proactive style. Proactive style has been used only in political crises, while reactive style has been used in all crises. Providing various scenarios in dealing with crises allows other organizations and individuals to be initiative in dealing with any similar future crises. This study serves as a guideline for choosing proper prospective measures and responses to crises.

Keywords: *Proactive, Reactive, Palestine, Palestinian Presidents, Leadership, Crisis*

1.0 Introduction

For political leaders, crisis management which includes preventing, preparation, response, and reconstruction is considered a tough task. Crisis management is always a tough mission as crisis leaders have faced difficulties to make the right decisions, especially in dealing with stress, organizational chaos, inaccurate information, and media pressure. Changes in the context and nature of recent crises make these

decisions almost elusive [1].

Mostly, presidents seem to be engaged in crisis management and reaction. Presidents pay more attention to new and unforeseen problems, and consequently, public opinion concerns about these new problems are more than other problems [2]. Crisis time may create an increased opportunity for the emergence of new leadership. The rise of charismatic leadership demonstrates an intersection of factors and forces with the leaders, followers, and the situation that they are involved in [3].

2.0 Problem statement

Crises must be dealt with, either before or after they occur to meet the needs of organizations. The proactive style comes before the occurrence of a crisis which is a preventive measure while the reactive style comes after the crisis and provides organizations and individuals with a solution to these crises. Thus, incorporating both proactive and reactive styles into crises by Palestinian Presidents becomes necessary and indispensable for managing the crises they faced.

To some extent, there is a small body of literature that addresses and concerns both reactive and proactive approaches to standards implementation [4, 5]. This study enhances the understanding of how proactive and reactive styles deal with crises which can help organizations and individuals to have better management of them. These proactive and reactive styles can be adopted by other organizations and individuals and enlighten them about the procedures that match the issues at their hand. Both reactive and proactive styles used by Palestinian Presidents leadership in crisis times have been examined in this study. Compared to other presidents and politicians, Palestinian Presidents have dealt with many crises due to the Israeli occupation which is one of the longest and most complex occupations.

This study examined how these styles have been used by Palestinian Presidents to cope with various types of crises at different times. The study focuses on Arafat and Abbas, who as Presidents of Palestine, are acknowledged as world leaders. Studying how the media report of their strategic moves in handling crises would be lessons for others to emulate.

3.0 Literature Review

Leadership is critical in handling crises. How leaders, as a critical representative of the political entity, accept and react to crises goes a long way in boosting stakeholder confidence. Leaders are visible during a crisis, directing and commanding events as they unfold to provide comfort to the affected parties. Their responses provide opportunities for transformation and renewal. Leaders are the spokesperson of the political entity, engaging themselves with the media and other parties to get their ideas across [6].

Our discussion is on leadership styles in dealing with crises. Each leader brings to the equation different styles of leadership, moving and shifting them as crisis takes different turns by the hour. We touch on two styles, the Proactive and Reactive Styles to understand the two Palestinian leaders in the manner they are portrayed to handle critical issues.

3.1 Proactive and Reactive Styles

The effectiveness and perceptions of leadership are associated with proactive personality. A proactive personality is an initiative to improve the current circumstances or create new circumstances; it includes challenging the current status instead of adopting it passively. Proactive people do not wait for the

opportunities and information passively, but they seek those opportunities and information actively to improve things [7]. Proactive personality is related to charismatic and transformational leadership. A positive association was found between self-reported proactive personality and charismatic leadership independent ratings. Proactive people show initiative, influence environmental change, find opportunities, act on them, and persevere until meaningful change. Proactive people transform the mission of their organizations, find the problems and solve them, and take responsibility to influence the world around them [8].

Proactivity focuses on future action which aims to create changes that have mostly led to several positive outcomes. Leaders are supposed to be more proactive in their thinking and planning for mastering the uncertainty of the environment, and bringing important changes without losing their focus on the main missions [9]. Proactivity is the degree of planning a program in anticipating the emergence of social trends and before the occurrence of crisis [10]. A proactive response is an approach that has control over an expected incident before its occurrence instead of responding to it after its occurrence [11]. Proactivity means taking control of a situation instead of responding to it, acting in anticipation of any future change or problem. Proactive behavior is a clear category of higher-order including problem prevention, taking charge, individual innovation, and voice. The concern of all of these behaviors is taking control and aim at making a change [12].

Proactive behavior includes identifying opportunities for improving the current status by creating suitable conditions [7]. Proactive behavior refers to anticipatory action taken by individuals to influence their environments and/or themselves. Acting in advance characterizes proactive behavior. Proactivity is not limited to unique actions set including taking charge or feedback-seeking but is a process that can be used in any set of actions through striving, planning, and anticipating to have an influence [13]. Proactive behavior is considered as a process that is active more than being passive or counteractive, being in secondary control, and transcendent more than being acquiescent [14].

A proactive response is taking action in anticipation of changes [15]. A proactive response is controlling a possible incident before it occurs instead of waiting to respond after the occurrence of the incident [11]. The proactive aspect includes developing preventive capacity in facing any unexpected disruptions [16]. Proactive pathways to sustainability rely on accurate and planned efforts of the members of organizations to achieve high-performance outcomes and sustainability levels [17]. Proactive people mostly scan for opportunities then act on them, taking actions, showing initiative, and persisting until making a meaningful change [7, 8, 14]. Proactive people tend to influence change, while reactive people are less initiative in making a change. The term proactive is mostly used to describe the behavior of people [14]. The proactive people do not blame the circumstances or environment to justify their behavior. Proactivity is based on actions, responsibilities, and initiatives. Taking the challenge of a proactive attitude might be oriented towards achievement and success. Acting proactively is doing something rather than being passive and watching [18]. Proactive strategies have been considered to be more effective than reactive strategies although there has been a belief about the effectiveness of reactive strategies [19].

Practicing a proactive corporate environment leads to having better environmental performance. Thus, proactive practices indicate the actions are taken ex-ante for preventing such emerging environmental issues [20]. Proactivity aims at the anticipation of emerging environmental and social issues [21]. Proactive strategies are both preventive and corrective [22]. The proactive plans tend to avert the crisis [23]. In times of crisis, a proactive personality has a positive influence on improving creativity and innovation [24]. Proactivity is helpful in protecting, recovering, restoring the reputational damage of organizations,

preventing the crisis [25]. The strategy of proactive crisis response contains several elements which are: leadership, communication transparency, long-term vision, intrinsic motivation, and promise to undertake precautionary and/or corrective actions [26].

Proactive approaches are reflected in the strategy of organizations to win competitive advantages [27]. A positive relationship was found between proactive personality and indicators of career success [28]. Also, there is a significant relationship between proactive personality and behavior of work, job autonomy, and co-worker trust [29]. A further proactive approach would lead to more control over workloads through getting more preventive work than the intervention of crisis [30]. Proactive personality is related to personality and work success and to success across the working life of individuals. A proactive personality leads to subjective outcomes of career success such as job and career satisfaction. The need for individuals and organizations to adopt a proactive change-oriented is increasing over time to remain competitive [31]. Proactive people have better job performance and high-level initiatives [32]. Considering the increasing complexity levels the organizations are challenged to be further proactive in their decision making. A proactive approach means initiating the actions and planning before the occurrence of an opportunity or threat [33].

Proactive behavior has two dimensions which are proactive problem solving and proactive idea implementation. Proactive problem solving refers to future-oriented responses and self-starting that intend to prevent the problem from recurrence by involving in solving it in a nonstandard and unusual way or by addressing its root cause. While implementation of proactive ideas includes taking charge of an idea by an individual whether by self-implementation of the idea or expressing it to others [29]. The proactive phase of conflict management contains thought processes and activities that can prevent the rise of a conflict or not controlling it [34]. Proactive management is a strategy that focuses on preventing any expected problems and recognizing them before they arise, and planning for the future and working to achieve them [35].

Proactivity is a strategy in itself and it is a way or philosophy for understanding crisis management. The policy of proactive communication includes designing actions of communication before starting the crisis. The objective of the policy of proactive communications is to regain control of the situation as much as possible. Proactivity characterized all the actions and interventions of communicative implemented by those responsible to solve the conflict [36]. Proactive public relations programs prevent crises and gain the support of the public when a crisis occurs [37]. The proactive approach of public relations has high efficiency in institutional conflict management which include having suitable measures to prevent a crisis before it occurs or control it immediately after it arose. The success of conflict prevention comes only through underlying the violence or conflict sources are improved and addressed by applying and adopting and public relations proactive principles more than conflict resolution reactive approach [38].

Proactivity is inextricably related to scanning for opportunities, being initiative, early intervention, anticipating any potential threats, taking control and future actions, and persisting until making a meaningful change that minimizes the damage. Proactive people do not wait for the opportunities and information passively, but they seek those opportunities and information actively to improve things. The proactive style becomes an indispensable part of the readiness and preparedness for any potential crisis and can help to prevent it before it gets worse.

In comparison, the reactive response is after the occurrence of the incident [11]. The reactive response is considered as reacting to environmental changes that have already occurred [15]. The reactive approach

means taking the action after the occurrence of an event or change [31]. The reactive response reacts only after the detection of an issue [11].

Reactive management deals with problems without any plan for the long term. Often, reactive organizations know the problem after receiving complaints about working conditions or circumstances. During such situations, it might be quite late for remedy. In some cases, combining both reactive and proactive styles may be necessary [35]. In the reactive phase of conflict management, a reaction must be done by the professional of public relations to events in the external environment of communication once the imminent conflict or issue reaches a critical effect level on the organization [34]. The reactive aspect includes taking quick and necessary actions in responding and recovering from any disruption and in ensuring the continuity of business [16].

The reactive plans tend to face the crisis [23]. The strategy of reactive crisis response includes various elements such as followership, short-term vision, opacity, extrinsic motivation, and no change in behavior [26]. A policy of reactive communications depends on communicating only when there is a strict necessity. The reactivity has a negative influence on the organization in the eyes of its public since it portrays it as defensive and lacking arguments or ideas to take the initiative [36]. A reactive strategy means responding to the experience of an organization, allowing it to address the failures effectively and efficiently [27]. Reactive environmental practices are related to worse environmental performance, and it is a symbolic behavior instead of being substantial initiatives of ex-ante environmental [20].

The reactive people have more focus on the results rather than taking the initiative [18]. Passive people show failing to identify opportunities or take advantage of them to change things. They depend on others to make the change, exhibit little initiative, and passively adapt to their circumstances and even endure, reflecting the reactive behavior towards their environments [14]. The less proactive individuals tend to adapt to their circumstances passively instead of changing them, and show little initiative [8]. Reactive people are showing the opposite style by being more passive and less proactive, they also fail to identify the opportunities to change things, and they prefer to adapt to the current circumstances than changing them [7].

Reactivity is reacting towards any situation or threat after its occurrence based on the circumstances and surroundings. Reacting or responding to any crisis should be planned or else it would cause so much damage to organizations or individuals. Reacting to the crisis at an early stage can help to end it and it is critical for the sustainability of organization or individuals.

3.2 Efficiency and Characteristics of Crisis Leadership

The deeply rooted belief in the significance of public leadership is joined by rapid and often superficial estimation of leadership performance. Despite the importance of symbolic performance, it is not the only performance dimension by which crisis leadership should be estimated [39]. The development of leadership itself is in crisis since it does not sufficiently combine the leadership concept that supports the practice of leadership in organizations. By exploring this concept, only leadership development can support an organization to meet the demands brought about by a crisis [40].

In history, it might be true that great leaders are those who turned crisis into prosperity. If one understands the requirements of corrective leadership conflict with the best practices of classical crisis management, maybe more leaders would be successful at turning crises around [1]. Governments,

organizations, and their leaders are affected when terrible things happen. But they will not be forgiven if they do not pay attention to rectifying the terrible things that happened. Many leaders have failed to act on or understand this lesson in the early phases of a crisis. The survival of an organization from a crisis with its operations, reputation, and financial condition is not only determined by the crisis severity but by the timeliness and response effectiveness [41].

Leadership is an essential matter in a crisis. Leadership is the responsibility of an individual who takes control and has the answer to every problem. The crisis response success is the result of development of proven leadership through an ongoing effort of the team in planning before the occurrence of an emergency, coordination during the crisis, and careful review after the crisis event [42]. In crisis times, leadership is considered an integral part of the outcome of successful crisis management. Obviously, crisis leaders are facing different challenges from normal operations. Leaders are required to employ skills and knowledge in crisis management beyond their day-to-day work. Leaders are required to be well prepared for any crisis or unknown challenges since crisis is not a usual part of the routine workflow [43].

During the crisis, leaders are expected to do their best to keep the people out of harm. Leaders are expected to provide directions and make tough decisions during difficult circumstances. They are expected by their organization's members and communities to minimize the influence of the crisis. When the response to a crisis is well made by policymakers so the damage will be reduced, and when they fail the damage will be increased [39].

Crisis leaders might try to push through the reform package and take advantage of the window of opportunity in order to show their effective leadership during the crisis, which is not unconscionable during normal times. Leaders can barely expect any dividend at all, in the contemporary crisis context. Even if the leaders are granted emergency powers, even if the coverage of the press is muted or supportive, and even if parliament supports remarkable measures, they cannot avoid radical reform if they do not at least try to establish support for themselves [1].

An organization must be guided by leaders through formal practice and planning with the understanding that a crisis is unlikely to go as planned and may need a flexible response. Leaders should lead the process of decision making while permanently assessing options. The key factor to the success of crisis management is leadership. Leadership ensures the preparation of business for any crisis in the pre-crisis phase, and ensures it is successfully navigating recovery and response [42].

During times of crisis, crisis leadership is more than managing public relations and corporate communication, since the activities of PR and communication are insufficient to cope with the crisis. Crisis leadership is not only about the parameters of legal responsibilities and risk management, but it is about the building of trust within an organization and its external stakeholders [44]. Under crisis circumstances, decision making does not only require identifying the priorities of interventions, but also the ability to manage and cope with that crisis to face the rare public resources. This means making the leadership function of communicating the effects of a crisis to citizens, stakeholders, and media [45].

Communicating in an effective way is very important for leaders. Effective communication is necessary so the response will be coherent and cohesive during managing a crisis, developing response teams, and garnering support for the time-consuming planning process. Within the business, individual groups will rigidly follow their recovery plans without considering the big picture and crisis response will not be well-coordinated if there is no strong leadership [42].

The communication process, public relations activities, contact with public and media, information gathering were important elements to manage and cope with a crisis [42, 44, 45]. Leaders need some skills to effectively manage the detection of the crisis phase. These skills contain interpersonal sensitivity, perspective-taking, and sense-making. Sense-making is helpful for crisis leaders to make connections between various information pieces, and to realize a series of events that may seem unrelated. Interpersonal sensitivity and perspective-taking allow crisis leaders to react to the best advantage of the stakeholders, empathize with others, and ensure the wellbeing of those involved in the crisis. Crisis leaders face the obstacles of gaining knowledge to come up with a crisis plan, understanding the cultural implications of their actions, and realizing cultural cues in a new context [46].

Crisis leadership is also considered as a timely and optimal assessment process of adverse conditions that influences whatever the reason is [47]. The need for leaders to handle the crisis in a clever way is undeniable. Such crises require leaders to act in exceptional ways to advance and threaten beyond routine strategies of problem-solving for resolution and to move beyond early emotional responses [48].

Crisis leadership is seen as an essential matter, category of behavior, the capacity of mobilization, characteristic of a person, the process of staff training and mobilization in a specific direction, and an attribute of a hierarchical position in the organization. The contribution of leaders to the leadership process is given through their skills, motivation, legitimacy, and personality [49].

Crisis leadership is important for several reasons: (1) The events of crisis are inevitable; (2) Nations and organizations' leaders can create a difference in the extent to which people are influenced by a crisis; (3) In the absence of crisis leadership, stakeholders who are adversely influenced by the crisis will not be able to recover from the damage; and (4) Regardless of the damage that has occurred because of the crisis, effective leadership can create the possibility of being better off following the crisis than it was before [44]. At least there are two elements that distinguish the leadership during a crisis: (1) The speed in taking actions and decisions; (2) The publicity and scrutiny that accompanies a firm and by extending its leaders during the crisis time. To be competent at crisis, leadership ultimately requires leaders to enhance their social and human capital through experience, education, training, natural ability, or practice [50]. Crisis leadership has two different phases: (1) Emergency phase: when the task is to buy time and settle the situation. (2) Adaptive phase: when to build the ability to succeed in a new reality and solve the implicit crisis causes [51].

Leadership during crisis times includes a main managerial competency. Regardless of the circumstances, requisite skills of effective leadership are the same whether in times of crisis or relative peace and being a good general leader during various crises [44]. Effective crisis leaders enhance a flexible mindset and demonstrate resilience within their employees in later crisis stages. Leaders draw on a particular set of competencies during the time of crisis that will lead the crisis to resolution in a way that enhances or preserves financial and other resources, employee commitment and morale, an overall image with stakeholders, and the firm's operational capabilities [50].

In a crisis, effective leaders grasp the importance of the underlying event, demonstrate situational awareness, and understand the possible influence of the crisis on the company and its stakeholders. Those leaders also show self-awareness and the ability to redirect their energy and attention to mobilize a rapid response and so they save the enterprise value of their companies. Effective leaders in the organization do not see crisis response as an interruption in their supervision but as the test of that supervision [42].

Learning from failures is a significant preparedness facilitator for both expected and existing crises. The situations of crisis highlight any problem in the activities and designs of an organizational system. When perceptions of leaders about risk are distinguished by ignoring or contradicting the preparation of a crisis, it is improbable that the organization will adopt practices of organizational crisis management. On the other hand, when leaders show concern about future crises risk, it is possible that the organization will foster programs of crisis management [53].

However, many executives ignore the other responsibilities of leadership that are connected with organizational crises. It can be caused by a lack of both job experience and formal training that prepare executives for a leading crisis. Leaders find themselves in need of moving beyond the emotional response to threat in such a way that allows them to engage in influential risk-taking, communication, and decision making during the containment stage and damage control of a crisis [50].

It is vital to realize the importance of crisis leadership to recover from the crisis and create better opportunities through taking the right actions and decisions. The right decisions rely on education, training, practice, and experience, not on emotions. During crisis time, the importance of leadership is highlighted as an essential matter to cope with any crisis. Understanding the crisis by leaders, being able to take control, being well prepared, planning, giving clear directions, facing different challenges, having creative decisions, communicating in an effective way, and having enough skills, knowledge and experience are important to settle that crisis despite its seriousness.

3.3 Leadership and Presidential Leadership

Leadership quality is crucial for institutions and organizations. Within all human activities, providing the necessary leadership and being able to step up the plate is the key achievement determinant. The need for leaders today at all levels is much greater than ever. Generally, leaders are not born, yet they are made; an individual becomes a leader when there is a need for a leader and that person rises to the occasion [53].

Leaders have the ability to know what should be done and how to accomplish it, who should do that, and what the result of that. Leaders have an innate ability to see the big picture, empowering their followers for achieving lofty and great goals, being able to delegate the job and attracting people for doing their task effectively and efficiently. Leaders are able to know their current status, what was achieved and what should be achieved, and how they are going to achieve that. Leaders also are able to deliver their vision and message to the followers [54].

Leadership is considered as a collective activity that gathers people to pursue what was found valuable for them. This collective pursuit of values made leadership not only an individual phenomenon but also a moral and social phenomenon [55].

By analyzing around 400 presidents' statements [56]; presidents have spoken about what leaders should do and what leadership is. Presidents through their statements have defined leadership as goal-oriented, a responsibility, morality, visionary, principles-based, and a search for the common good. However, presidents mostly complemented these definitions with more discussions about what leaders do [56]. The essence of the presidency is leadership, but effective presidential leadership prioritizes national demands against pressures of their partisan [57].

Often, it is thought that charismatic leaders are emerging in crisis times. In the condition of stress, leaders were significantly perceived as more charismatic than leaders in the condition of no-stress. Leaders who have experienced stress conditions before the intervention of crisis have shown better task performance and greater charismatic behavior levels than those who did not experience stress conditions. Leaders might be able to face the debilitating influence of stress only through increased experience in several situations of crisis [58].

Charismatic leaders seem to have the influence that is helpful for creating remarkably powerful degrees of consistency between cognitions of individuals, feelings behavior, and behavior outcomes, or increase constancy if they existed before in weak form [59]. The charisma of leaders is a combination of personal traits including the ability to bear dissonance and ambiguity; the personal appearance [54].

From the argument above, it can be understood that being a leader does not mean having only special skills, knowledge, or personal characteristics but adhering to values, beliefs, integrity, morality, virtue, and the common good. Leaders can also make other people leaders by empowering and motivating them. Leaders prioritize public interests over their private interests.

4.0 Methodology

This study used content analysis to examine both proactive and reactive styles used by Palestinian Presidents leadership during crises. Qualitative and quantitative content analyses are complementary to each other and combining them is essential to understand and determine the meanings of media texts and their influence on the audience [60].

A total of 313 news stories in the daily issues of *New Straits Times* (NST) newspaper related to proactive and reactive styles on Palestinian Presidents leadership were found. Both microfilm and microfiche were used to retrieve the data of this study. This newspaper has been selected since it is controlled by UMNO, the ruling party in Malaysia [61, 62], its wide circulation and since it comes in the English language which can reach a wider audience. The time frame of this study was from 1996 to 2016. The year 1996 coincides with the first Palestinian elections until President Arafat's death in 2004, and the year 2005 coincides with the success of President Abbas in the election until the decrease in coverage about Palestinian President in 2016. In this study, each of the selected news stories served as a unit of analysis. The instrument for data collection was the coding sheet. Face validity was implemented in this study. Face validity is offered implicitly through reflecting the nature of categories which make them seem logical [63]. It is suitable by having high agreement among researchers [64], and achieving it comes through an informed judgment of those researchers. It is a part of the internal validity test or assessments.

To ensure the reliability of study, three coders were assigned to code the same news stories. The coders used the coding book as their manual and the coding sheet as their instrument. Besides, the coders participated independently in a pretest trial round to analyze and code the stories. The coders received training and were briefed about the constructs under investigation and the characteristics that needed to be looked at during the analysis of the news stories. The coders started the intercoder reliability after their agreement on the guidelines and instructions, and when they have clarified the coding process. This process was to avoid the bias of any coder and to insure the objectivity, reliability, and validity.

Categorizing and coding proactive and reactive styles in this study were modified from the studies of [9, 10, 11, 14, 15, 18, 33]. Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data of this study. The data was cleaned, checked and regulated to ensure its accuracy. The quantitative analysis included descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentage of occurrence, and cross-tabulations. Besides, qualitative interpretation was implemented to support the quantitative data.

5.0 Results and Discussion

Both proactive and reactive styles used by Palestinian Presidents as covered by New Straits Time are discussed in this section. Table 1 shows these styles. The reactive style was found in 67.7% of the selected 313 news stories, compared to 32.3% of stories that included proactive styles. Proactive and reactive styles were used in three main types of crises including political, social, and economic crises. The vast majority of the crises were political due to the severity of the Palestinian-Israeli conflict. These political crises include several issues such as the peace process, foreign pressure, Israeli attacks, threats, blockades, and Palestinian-Israeli clashes. The social crises included information leakage, and Israeli slanders and rumors. Finally, the economic crises were financial that occurred during the tenure of President Abbas due to abstain by the Israeli government to transfer the collected taxes to the Palestinian Authority under the terms of their accords [66,67] that Israel should collect the taxes within the Palestinian borders and then transfer them to the Palestinian.

TABLE 1
Proactive and Reactive Styles

Type of response	Frequency	Percentage
Proactive	101	32.3
Reactive	212	67.7
Total	313	100.0

This study analyzed coverage of New Straits Time on the proactive and reactive styles used by both Palestinian Presidents. Table 2 compares these styles. For President Arafat, reactive style shaped 63% of the news stories compared to 37% of news stories that included proactive style. For President Abbas, reactive styles shaped 78.4% of news stories followed by 21.6% of news stories that included proactive style. It can be seen that President Abbas has a more proactive style and less reactive style than President Arafat.

The following quotations show examples of the proactive style of both Presidents Arafat and Abbas during their tenures:

Arafat has warned that new violence could erupt if the Washington summits failed (NST, 17 Jan 1998).

President Yasser Arafat, addressing Palestinians on the day a peace deadline with Israel expired, accused the Israeli government of keeping the Middle East mired in tension (NST, 6 May 1999).

Yasser Arafat proposed that he and Ariel Sharon simultaneously call for an end to violence, but the Israeli Prime Minister was cool to the idea, insisting the Palestinians leader issue stop-fire orders to gunmen instead, advisors said today (NST, 21 Apr 2001).

Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas will announce today a referendum in establishing

a Palestinian state alongside Israel, likely to be held on July 31, an aide said on Thursday (NST, 10 Jun 2006).

President Mahmoud Abbas said Israel was offering “nothing we can build on” for peace and that without progress, he will seek United Nations’ recognition of Palestinian statehood in September (NST, 26 May 2011).

Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas repeated an offer on Monday to restart peace talks with Israel after a United Nations vote to recognise Palestine as an observer state later this month (NST, 14 Nov 2014).

On the other hand, the reactive style of both Presidents Arafat and Abbas is presented in the following sentences:

Palestinian President Yasser Arafat accused Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu of “sabotaging the peace process” by authorising new Jewish settlement activity in the occupied territories (NST, 7 Aug 1996).

A halt to Jewish settlement expansion, including in Arab East Jerusalem, is Arafat’s condition for resuming talks with Israel but Netanyahu rules it out (NST, 29 May 1997).

President Yasser Arafat demanded immediate international action today “to stop this military madness” after Israeli killed 10 Palestinians, most of them civilians, in air strikes in Gaza Strip (NST, 22 Oct 2003).

Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas has rejected an Israeli peace process because it does not provide for a contiguous Palestinian state with Jerusalem as its capital, Abbas’s office said today (NST, 14 Aug 2008).

Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas of Tuesday warned of legal and diplomatic action to stop Israeli settlement expansion, on the eve of a new peace mission by United States Secretary of State John Kerry (NST, 2 Jan 2014).

Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas has threatened to turn to the International Criminal Court over Israel’s refusal to fully release hundreds of millions of dollars in tax monies owed to the Palestinian Authority (NST, 7 Apr 2015).

TABLE 2

Type of Response by both Presidents

Type of response	Frequency of Arafat	Percentage of Arafat	Frequency of Abbas	Percentage of Abbas
Proactive	80	37	21	21.6
Reactive	136	63	76	78.4
Total	216	100.0	97	100.0

6.0 Conclusion

The results of this study revealed that both Palestinian Presidents Arafat and Abbas used both proactive and reactive styles in their efforts to cope with various crises faced during their presidential tenure. However, President Arafat used a proactive style more than President Abbas. Organizations and or individuals have to deal with any crisis whether proactively before its occurrence or reactively after its occurrence. They must not stand idly by in the face of the crises otherwise these crises will cause great damage for them. Crises are unavoidable and no organization or individual are vulnerable or exempted from crises. Monitoring the threats

and being proactive is very essential in alleviating the influence of crises. Any imminent threat should not be neglected and to be considered seriously by dealing with it proactively. Also, once an unexpected threat occurs and causes tremendous pressure a reactive effort is required in this case.

The results of this study can direct and guide other organizations and individuals about the proper measures to be taken in case of facing similar crises. The results can help to debilitate influence of future crisis by reflecting how Palestinian Presidents experienced similar crisis and solve it. The results have proven that Palestinian Presidents were effective and charismatic leaders especially in dealing with severe crises due to the complexity of conflict with Israel during their tenures. Experiencing several crisis and dealing with them in a proper manner proven their charisma especially comparing with other leaders who never had a similar experience. The efforts of Palestinian Presidents in dealing with crises have hindered piled them up and complicating the situation.

7.0 References

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